

RATIONAL FLOW MODELING

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ABSTRACT

The methodology used to develop computational techniques capable of predicting the dynamic response of submersible vehicles in highly dynamic maneuvers is discussed. Applications of the techniques are presented for both aerodynamic and submersible configurations documenting the results of prediction of normal force and pitching moment for the complete vehicle, spanwise normal force distributions on tail surfaces, and the vorticity distribution on the flow field at three axial stations.

INTRODUCTION

A long-standing problem in the design of free-swimming and towed underwater vehicles is that of predicting vehicle dynamics during highly dynamic, extreme maneuvers. The development of semi-empirical methods for generic vehicle geometric configurations provided a significant step toward solving this problem; however, the median to high angles of attack and sideslip together with the associated viscous flow regimes require a more complex modeling approach to properly predict dynamic vehicle behavior.

In order to solve this problem, NCSC is currently developing a nonlinear vehicle dynamics technique called "rational" flow modeling for submersible vehicles of general configuration. Initiated as an Independent Research project, the approach is that of identifying the dominant flow phenomena and then developing simple models governing their behavior. For example, for underwater vehicles the formation of body vortices and their interaction with fin tip vortices are the dominant flow phenomena at high angles of attack. This technology, originally applied by the aerospace community to missile dynamics, is now being adapted to submersible vehicles and extended to handle unsteady motion.

A brief description is presented of the methods, their application, and results obtained for both aerodynamic and submersible configurations.

NONLINEAR FLOW PHENOMENA

When a submersible operates at high angles of incidence large amounts of vorticity are introduced in the flow through hull crossflow boundary layer separation and the strong trailing vortex wakes from appendages (see Figure 1). The resulting near-wake flow about the submersible is very complex. Important vortex interference effects occur between hull shed vorticity and the fin trailing wakes as the combined vorticity trails aft along the hull length. The magnitude of shed vorticity and vortex interaction influence hull pressures and downstream fin loadings. The net effect of the vortex wake is to generate important nonlinear hydrodynamic forces and moments acting on the submersible.

MODELING APPROACH

In order to predict the hydrodynamics of submersibles operating in the nonlinear flight regime, the characteristics of the separated near-wake flow and the effect on surface pressures must be accurately modeled. A purely analytical approach to this problem would require the solution of the full equations of motion for the fluid (e.g. 3-D Navier-Stokes equations). While this method is the most general and hence the most powerful, current numerical methods available to solve these equations are difficult to apply and require large amounts of computer time and storage. The rational flow approach overcomes this difficulty by attacking the problem from a different perspective. Rather than attempting a direct solution of the Navier-Stokes equations, the important features of the nonlinear flow are directly simulated using simple physical models.

The appeal of the rational flow approach lies in its generality and computational affordability. Arbitrary submersible geometries can be considered without the need for major empirical inputs. Execution times are small enough to allow repeated use of the method. These advantages make the rational flow approach optimal for use in the design and analysis of submersible

vehicles. A brief description of the major modeling components is given below.

Hull Boundary Layer Separation - The crossflow boundary layer separation is predicted using a criteria proposed by Stratford^{1,2} and modified for 3-D effects. Separation is predicted for laminar, transitioned, and turbulent boundary layers, with the transition region specified a priori.

Lifting Surfaces - The linear component of lift is modeled using the vortex-lattice-lifting-surface method. The nonlinear component of lift is predicted with the Polhamus leading-edge suction analogy.³ A stall limit is included using a method from the DATCOM.⁴

Vortex Wake - The impulsive flow analogy⁵ is used to model the 3-D steady flow field as an equivalent 2-D unsteady flow field. This analogy allows the near-wake flow to be solved in the crossflow plane of the body at a discrete number of axial stations. The continuous sheets of vorticity shed by the hull and appendages are approximated in the crossflow plane using discrete 2-D vortices.

The calculation procedure begins at a crossflow plane near the body nose. The full Bernoulli equation is used to compute the potential pressure distribution on the body which is then checked against the separation criteria. If separation is found, point vortices are placed in the flow at the predicted separation points. Each vortex is allowed to convect downstream and influence the flow field at subsequent crossflow planes.

COMPARISON WITH DATA

Airship hull data⁶ and wind tunnel model data^{7,8} were used in the preliminary validation of the rational flow model. These data provide the gross force and moment measurements as well as detailed pressure distributions required to verify the model. A sample of the results is presented in Figures 2 through 4.

Figure 2 presents comparisons of normal force and pitching moment coefficients on a 1/40-scale model of the Akron airship hull.⁶ Two theory curves are given for the rational flow model: one with and the other without the leeward separation model. Without the separation model, the potential flow about the hull is simulated using a distribution of point sources and sinks along the body axis and doublets in the crossflow plane. Agreement with the data is very good for $\alpha < 4^\circ$. At these small angles the boundary layer is attached along the full length of the hull except for a small region near the stern where the axial boundary layer thickens and separates. This is accounted for in the rational flow model by the use of an equivalent base area

near the aft end of the hull where separation occurs. For angles of attack greater than 4° , crossflow separation of the boundary layer significantly effects the forces and moments. The agreement between theory and data is excellent throughout the nonlinear range when the leeward separation model is included.

The effect of crossflow separation on the predicted hull pressures is evidenced in Figure 3. At the angle of attack considered ($\alpha = 20^\circ$), the leeward pressures on the afterbody are strongly influenced by the hull vortex wake. The longitudinal distribution of leeward pressures is predicted well using the separation model.

Rotating arm experiments for a 4:1 ellipsoid body of revolution provide pressure data for the body in steady translation and rotation.⁸ Figure 4 presents comparisons of longitudinal pressures for the body pitching nose downward at a steady rate of rotation ($\alpha = 20^\circ$, $q' = -0.0717^*$). Agreement with the data is very good for both the windward and leeward pressures. While the rate of rotation is small, these comparisons show the model's ability to predict the effects of flow separation under more complicated flow conditions.

APPLICATION TO A SUBMERSIBLE CONFIGURATION

A generic submersible is considered in this section to illustrate the ability of the rational flow model to predict the nonlinear hydrodynamic characteristics of a fully appended configuration. The configuration, shown at the top of Figure 5, is a body of revolution with three forward fins and four tail fins. Figure 5 presents total normal force and pitching moment coefficients versus angle of sideslip (β) for the submersible undergoing a steady port turn ($r' = -0.4^*$) and rolled into the turn by an angle $\phi = 20^\circ$. Significant forces and moments are generated in the vertical plane due to fin loading and downstream vortex interaction. These out-of-plane forces and moments play a key role in the nonlinear hydrodynamics of submersibles with asymmetric geometries.

Figure 6 presents detailed load information on the tail planes for the submersible at $\beta = 8^\circ$. The spanwise normal force distribution and total normal force coefficient are given for each tail plane. High crossflow velocities present at the stern account for the heavy loading on the vertical planes.

In Figure 7 cross-sectional views at three axial stations detail the near-wake flow of the submersible. The first axial station, located immediately behind the three forward fins, shows the trailing vorticity shed by each of the fins.

*Rates of rotation are nondimensionalized by the hull length and free-stream velocity.

This vorticity represents the trailing legs of the vortex lattices, modeled by 2-D point vortices in the crossflow plane. At the second axial station, the fin vortices have convected downstream and a small vortex wake has formed on the leeside of the hull. The hull separation is not symmetric due to the influence of the fin vortices. A strong leeside wake is apparent at the final axial station considered.

CONCLUSIONS

Results presented in this paper show that the rational flow approach is capable of modeling the nonlinear hydrodynamics of submersibles with no major empirical inputs. The rational flow approach represents the most advanced modeling tool available to predict the hydrodynamics of submersibles operating in highly dynamic maneuvers.

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FIGURE 1. SKETCH OF THE FLOW FIELD ADJACENT TO A SUBMERSIBLE UNDERGOING STEADY MOTION

FIGURE 2. MEASURED AND PREDICTED NORMAL FORCE AND PITCHING MOMENT COEFFICIENT ON AKRON AIRSHIP HULL

FIGURE 3. MEASURED AND PREDICTED LONGITUDINAL PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION ON AKRON AIRSHIP HULL, $\alpha = 20^\circ$

FIGURE 4. MEASURED AND PREDICTED PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION ON A 4:1 ELLIPSOID BODY OF REVOLUTION; $\alpha = 20^\circ$, $q' = -0.0717$

FIGURE 5. PREDICTED NORMAL FORCE AND PITCHING MOMENT ON APPENDED SUBMERSIBLE IN A STEADY TURN, $\phi = 20^\circ$, $r' = -0.4$

FIGURE 6. SPANWISE NORMAL FORCE DISTRIBUTIONS AND TOTAL LOADS ON TAIL PLANES, $\beta = 8^\circ$, $\phi = 20^\circ$, $r' = -0.4$

S FIN VORTEX
 O UPPER BODY VORTEX
 X LOWER BODY VORTEX

(a) $X/L = .26$

(b) $X/L = .61$

(c) $X/L = .84$

FIGURE 7. VORTICITY DISTRIBUTIONS AT THREE AXIAL STATIONS, $\beta = 8^\circ$, $\phi = 20^\circ$, $r' = -0.4$